

First records for the orb-web spider *Arachnura scorpionoides* Vinson, 1863 from South Africa (Araneae: Araneidae)

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Abstract

The scorpion tail orb-web spider *Arachnura scorpionoides* Vinson, 1863 is for the first time reported from South Africa. This species has been recorded throughout South Africa, extending its current distribution range in Africa from Congo (DRC), Ethiopia, Seychelles, Mayotte, Madagascar, Mauritius and Réunion to South Africa. The general morphology of the species is described. Life photographs are provided with notes on their behaviour, distribution and conservation.

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Arachnura* of the family Araneidae is known as the tailed spider or scorpion tail spider (Arachne-spider and nura-tail). The genus was described by Vinson (1863) with *Arachnura scorpionoides* as the type species. The genus is represented by 12 species and has a wide distribution known from India, China, Africa and Australia (World Spider Catalogue 2020). *Arachnura scorpionoides* is the only species known Africa and has so far been reported from the Congo (DRC), Ethiopia, Seychelles, Mayotte, Madagascar, Mauritius and Réunion. The male is still unknown. As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa) large numbers of specimens were sampled and became available for research (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2015). Between the sampled material the scorpion tail orb-web spider *A. scorpionoides* has been identified. This paper reports on the morphological variation observed, their behaviour and occurrence in South Africa.

METHODS

During the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa) requests were made for photographs of species for the SANSa Virtual Museum (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2012). Several sets of photographs of *A. scorpionoides* have been received from the public. Photographs in laboratory taken by a Leica V3.6.0 system. The new records reported on here are from specimens collected during SANSa surveys. The voucher specimens are deposited in the National Collection of Arachnida of the Agricultural Research Council Plant Health and Protection division.

TAXONOMY

Arachnura scorpionoides Vinson, 1863

Arachnura scorpionoides Vinson, 1863: 291, 310, pl. 13, f. 1 (Df).

Hapalochrota caudata Keyserling, 1864: 82, pl. 3, f. 6-11 (Df).

Arachnura scorpionoides Uyemura, 1976b: 26, f. 1.2, 4, 6, 2.1-2, 3.1, 4.1 (f).

Arachnura scorpionoides Saaristo, 2010: 33, f. 4.1-2 (f); Cazanove & Begue, 2018: 22; Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2014.

Figure 1a-b *Arachnura scorpionoides* female from Kruger National Park (a) lateral view (b) dorsal view Photo credit Vida van der Walt

Diagnostic characters: Size: females TL 7–10 mm. This species is very distinct in the tail like shape of the abdomen (Fig. 1a). Cephalothorax broad, narrowing anteriorly. In alcohol material dark markings visible medially and around border (Fig. 2a). Eyes in two rows with posterior median eyes closely spaced, median ocular area longer than wide (Fig. 2a); lateral eyes closely spaced on lateral border. Abdomen broad with two horn like projections protruding over the cephalothorax in a V-shape; it then tapers into a long tail with soft lobes on the tips (Fig. 3c). The front legs are stronger than the rest and kept close to the body when alive. Some change in colour was observed as the seasons change (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2009) specimens are more yellow in summer (Fig. 2a) and becoming duller brown in winter (Figs 2b,2c). In a recent paper by Cazanove & Begue (2018) they observed similar colour variations in *A. scorpionoides* from Réunion. They reported on a yellow, fawn and brown form.

Figure 2a-b. (a) *Arachnura scorpionoides* female carapace dorsal view; (b) female epigynum.

Fig. 2b *Arachnura scorpionoides* female dorsal view

Figure 3a–d. *Arachnura scorpionoides* female (a) female yellow photograph Gawie le Roux ; (b) brown form female hanging in web photograph Karen Fourie; (c) female lateral view showing soft lobes at the tip photo Andrea Sander

BEHAVIOUR

Arachnura scorpionoides construct a permanent but incomplete orb-web with an open hub. The web is suspended on an angle and has a V-shaped section missing from the top of the web. In autumn/winter, the female produces a series of woolly brownish egg sacs which she strings together in a line from the centre of the web to fill the missing section. The spider took up position at the bottom of the string in the centre of the web (Figs 4a,4b.) The female spider can curl her tail up over her back like a scorpion if she is disturbed (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2009).

Figure 4a–b. *Arachnura scorpionoides* female (a) female in web below egg sacs photo Roelien Dreyer; (b) female hanging in web photograph photo Cynthia le Roux.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION

Congo (DRC), Ethiopia, Seychelles, Mayotte, Madagascar, Mauritius, Réunion. News records: South Africa

MATERIAL EXAMINED

SOUTH AFRICA. Eastern Cape: Port Elizabeth (-33.95 S; 25.61 E), F. Schultz leg., 1.ii.1974, 1 imm. (NCA 76/250). **KwaZulu-Natal:** iSimangaliso Wetland Park, False Bay Park (-27.92 S, 32.27 E), L. Prendini leg., 5.i.1989, 1 f (NCA 89/525); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Fanie’s Island (-28.10 S, 32.45 E), M. Filmer leg., 23.vii.1990, imm f (NCA 90/245); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Mkuzi Game Reserve (-27.63 S, 32.25 E), M. Filmer leg. 22.vii.1990, 1 f (NCA 90/224);

iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Sodwana Bay National Park (-27.40 S, 32.6 E), M. Filmer leg, 14.x.1990, 1 f (NCA 91/689); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87 S, 32.24 E), C. Haddad leg, 3.iv.2004, 1f (NCA 2004/1223); Phinda Game Reserve (-27.72 S, 32.38 3), S. Lovell leg., 5.iii.1989, 1f (NCA 2004/678); Vernon Crookes Nature Reserve (-30.27 S, 30.57 E), R. Maartens leg., 25.iii.1986, 1f (NCA 86/582). **Limpopo:** Lajuma Mountain Retreat (-23.03, 29.45), A. Fischer leg. 3.ii.2005, 1f (NCA 2006/1036). **Mpumalanga:** Lowveld National Botanical Gardens (-25.47, 31.00), A. Leroy leg., 10.iii.2007, 1f (NCA 2008/2949); Pilgrims Rest (- 24.89, 30.75), M. Filmer leg., 29.xii.1988, 1f (NCA 90/67); Schagen (-25.43, 30.80), M. vd Berg leg., 19.viii.1997, tree fogging, 1f (NCA 98/184). **North West:** Brits (-25.62, 27.77) , M. Filmer leg., 28.ii.1989, 1f (NCA 89/584). **Western Cape:** Table Mountain National Park (-33.82, 18.48), N. Larsen leg., 15.ii.2010, 1f (NCA 2010/623).

SANSA VM Photo gallery; Tsitsikamma National Park (Gawie Le Roux) VM SANSA 2010/107; Stilbaai (K.Geldenhuis) VM SANSA 2008/389, Bellville (K. Marais), VM SANSA 2010/342; Port Elizabeth (Le Roux Willie & Cynthia) VM SANSA 2009/508 Kruger National Park (Vida vd Walt) VM SANSA 2009/405.

Fig. 5. Map showing the distribution of *Arachnura scorpionoides* in South Africa

HABITAT

The species was sampled in the Fynbos, Savanna (Foord *et al.* 2011), Indian Ocean Coastal Belt and Thicket biomes. The species was also sampled in macadamia orchards (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2001) during tree fogging. In the Ndumo Game Reserve the species was sampled from the Broadleaf woodland; Ficus forest riparian forests along Pongola and Usutu rivers and Subtropical bush (Haddad *et al.* 2006).

CONSERVATION

An African endemic recorded from six African countries. In South Africa, it is known from six provinces and >10 protected areas (Fig. 5). Due to its wide geographical range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

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